

Deliverable 4.1

Interim Impact Assessment

Report

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List of abbreviations

CAPs	Collective Awareness Platforms
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
WP	Workpackage
ZSI	Centre for Social Innovation – ZSI

Definition

Careables - an open solution that aims to improve the quality of life for people with unmet particular needs or facing physical limitations. Careables are often co-designed, replicable, accessible, adjustable and shareable online using digital technologies. Careables is a relatively new category, that promises more readily customized solutions and a more horizontal and collaborative approach to health and care.

1. Executive Summary

This report presents the outcomes from the first evaluation activities conducted in the careables project, which were based on a set of quantitative and qualitative data collection instruments and a defined set of indicators presented in D4.1 Evaluation and Impact Assessment Framework.

The evaluation activities aimed to collect formative feedback on careables co-creation events organized in three European countries, namely Italy, Germany and the Netherlands. These co-creation events assembled people with specific health needs, makers, designers, health professionals and European citizens in trans-disciplinary teams which successfully co-created open healthcare solutions. These solutions addressed very specific needs of people who suffer from disabilities or illness.

The collected evaluation data deepened our understanding on organizational aspects like the timing of the events, required facilitation processes, group creation processes, process moderation, agenda setting etc. The analysis of evaluation data also helped to reveal the broad range of expectations that drove participants' initial involvement, as well as ongoing motivational factors that helped to keep participants engaged throughout the co-creation process.

The summative evaluation showed that the participation in the co-creation events resulted in some important effects on the participating individuals like learning and knowledge exchange, collaboration and networking, a feeling of empowerment, or increased awareness for the topic of health & making. In addition, having a working prototype at the end of a co-design process is crucial for the user experience. We have clear indications that the participants in the co-creation, whether people with a specific need or those supporting them in the design and creation process, experience great satisfaction at the end of the process, when they present a working careables prototype. Unfortunately, not all teams succeeded in this attempt and we also discuss the reasons why this happened in this document. Chapter 7 gives a detailed summary of the evaluation outcomes from the co-creation events.

Next to the co-creation events, the careables platform is another important target of evaluation activities. The careables platform aims to improve the access to well documented careables, allows for the replication of careables and supports the knowledge exchange and networking in the careables community. The evaluation of the platform will be a focus of the upcoming project activities, but this report already presents the method of assessing user acceptance factors of the platform as well as a preview into first insights from evaluation activities that are performed at the time when writing this deliverable in Chapter 7.

Finally, Chapter 6 outlines how our project achievements link to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG), such as goal 3, good health and wellbeing, but also to

complementary goals that are more on responsible production and consumption, new modes of manufacturing and equality.

2. Introduction

The main objectives of workpackage 4 are to monitor the performance of the project, evaluate the expected outcomes and assess its potential impact. With these aims, data are continually gathered and feed a set of monitoring criteria and impact metrics that have been developed in the initial stage of careables and presented in D4.1. Evaluation and Impact Assessment Framework. Part of D4.1 is also a prioritization of the project objectives and a description of their implication for evaluation (see table 1). This prioritization helps to focus the evaluation activities.

Table 1: Overview of objectives and ranking of priority

Objectives	Implication for evaluation	Priority ranking
improve the accessibility of open source products	Accessibility of the platform and the open source products shared in the platform is increased if different target groups can better find, understand and communicate about careables. We will rely on existing criteria for accessibility, usability and usefulness and evaluate them with careables target users.	1 (highest)
foster knowledge exchange	Knowledge exchange is closely related to high quality collaborations. Potential effects of knowledge exchange are changes in knowledge/attitudes, practices and performance; all three aspects are relevant for the evaluation, as well as a better understanding of effective knowledge exchange processes.	2
establish collaboration between the communities	Quality of collaboration as defined by different studies; in the case of careables collaboration can take place and be evaluated in the co-design and local working sessions as well as in the online activities; thus, both aspects need to be considered, with a focus on the local collaboration in the Fablabs.	3

allow anyone to replicate formats	Replication is closely connected to the aspect of accessibility and usability of the platform and the documentation process for careables. The evaluation of this objective will thus be aligned with the objective on accessibility.	4
improve quality of life or services provided	The dimensions of “Quality of life” defined by different studies (e.g. Fitzpatrick et al. 1992; WHO); we can refer back to these studies and select the most suitable dimension for careables, also in alignment with the taxonomy/classification of careables. We will approach this topic mainly in a qualitative way.	5 (lowest)

To evaluate the set of above-mentioned objectives a set of qualitative and quantitative evaluation instruments were used and presented in Chapter 3 of this document. Chapter 4-5 present the detailed evaluation outcomes and Chapter 6 introduces our main lessons learned, conclusions and an outlook for the upcoming evaluation activities.

3. Overview of evaluation activities

Evaluation is an ongoing process and connects strongly with the project activities, which centered in the first half of the project around the careable co-creation events and processes initiated in Italy, Germany and the Netherlands, as well as a stepwise development of the careables platform and its content, which will be deployed and largely disseminated in the beginning of 2020.

Evaluation of the co-creation processes and its impact

The co-creation processes were conceptualized and organized differently by partners in Italy, Germany and the Netherlands. We had short-term formats implemented in Germany and Italy by Agile Heap and OpenDot and one long-term format tested by WAAG in the Netherlands. Internal reflections by the event organizers on the usefulness of the formats and their main lessons learned led to the Deliverable “D1.2. Training Kit: On prototyping series for healthcare innovation”.

In addition to these internal reflections, event participants were involved in evaluation activities, which are described in more detail in this document. Participants were approached via questionnaires and/or interviews to learn about the usefulness of the events, collect formative feedback on the events, as well as drivers and barriers of participation. The following table shows the number of data collected from event participants:

Table 2: Evaluation instruments and participants

OpenHealth HACKademy (Agile Heap) I	OpenHealth HACKademy (Agile Heap) II	Health&Care SummerSchool (OpenDot)	MakeHealth: Prototyping Serie (WAAG)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Questionnaire (10 participants) • Questionnaire (6 facilitators) • User journey interviews (8) • Interviews on drivers & barriers (4) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Questionnaire (8 participants) • Questionnaire (9 facilitators) • User journey interviews (8) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Questionnaire (9 participants) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Questionnaire (14 participants)

The different formats, evaluation instruments and results are presented in Chapter 4 of this deliverable.

User acceptance testing via walkthroughs and think aloud

In addition to collecting feedback on the co-creation events, this deliverable introduced to the method of user acceptance testing of our careables platform. The careables and welder platform has been continually developed with a strong involvement of its future users. This involvement is described in D3.1 and led to a redesign of the platform in 2019; the second version of careables.org was launched in October 2019. This second version was then more deeply evaluated with regard to user acceptance and usability including test participants from Italy, Austria, Germany and the Netherlands.

At the time of writing this deliverable, the user tests were still under way, but what we introduce here is the method of user testing and how we will take up the results in the further development.

In addition to the user acceptance testings, usage statistics will provide us with more insights in the uptake of the careables platform and welder app. The platform will be specifically promoted and communicated to the large stakeholder groups of the consortium in January 2020. This is when we expect interested users to access our platform and start interacting with it. Nevertheless first access statistics to the early versions of the platform are presented in this deliverable in Chapter 5.

4. Evaluation of careables co-creation processes & events

In the following chapter we will present the evaluation of the co-creation processes in Germany, Italy and the Netherlands.

4.1. HACKademy I (Agile Heap)

In the following chapter the evaluation of the HACKademy is presented. The HACKademy was a co-creation format organized by the partner Agile Heap in cooperation with the project “Match my Maker” that is led by be able e.V., a non-profit organization with expertise in co-creative processes in the field of accessibility and inclusion. So far it was organized two times, and a third event is foreseen for 2020.

At the Open Health HACKademy, interdisciplinary teams with students from different disciplines, people with disabilities and makers jointly develop careables “cases”. Case owners are the people with disabilities. They join the HACKademy as the experts of their “lebenswelt”, presenting their specific needs and an idea for a potential careable. Other participants, like students, makers or health professionals, can then apply to take part in the HACKademy and chose one of the proposed cases that they wish to support with their work. Teams are pulled together for each case and experienced coaches from the fields of electronic prototyping, coding, digital fabrication and design thinking support these teams.

4.1.1. Introduction to HACKademy I

The first HACKademy took place in the FabLab machBar Potsdam from 1st to 17th of March 2019. The main activities of the HACKademy were organized on the three weekends in this period, namely 2.-3., 9.-10. and 16.-17. March; the weeks in-between were understood as time to voluntarily contribute to the cases from remote locations at home. At the week-ends participants were provided with an agenda and input sessions that led them through the design thinking process, introduced them to the most important digital fabrication tools and skills and showcased other careables; also external experts were introduced as speakers to these input sessions. The HACKademy ended with a presentation of all developed prototypes and students could also gain credit points for their participation.

All together the event involved the following participant numbers:

Table 3: HACKademy I participants

HACKademy	At the Open Health HACKademy, four interdisciplinary teams jointly developed careables.	1.- 17.3.2019	24 participants
HACKademy Meet Up	Testing first HACKademy Ideas with interested guests after first design sprint	3.2.2019	29 participants
HACKademy Meet Up	Interim presentation and feedback with externals and all interested guests	9.3.2019	31 participants
HACKademy Meet Up	Accompany the final presentation of HACKademy	17.3.2019	70 participants

HACKademy I had four teams which worked on four cases:

Team Eule (engl. Owl)

The careable supports a deaf young man, who wishes to communicate with others without the use of sign language. The careable translates spoken words to written text on the man's mobile phone. He types his message to the mobile phone and the information is presented to his surrounding via a screen integrated in a synthetic owl.

The team aimed at developing a first prototype that could be tested by the careable owner in the run-time of the HACKademy. With this aim the functionality of the prototype had to be reduced (initial ideas were more complex, as the team initially wanted to provide reading capabilities to the careable too).

Team Bellybutton

The careable supports people with gastro stoma. The "bellybutton" is like an outlet that connects the stomach with the outside for parenteral nutrition. It needs to be replaced every three months– an activity, which is neither dangerous nor very complex, but hardly done by relatives themselves. Even

inexperienced medical assistants have respect when changing the button. Thus the bellybutton project aims to develop a dummy, which allows people to practice the exchange of bellybuttons.

The team developed two different prototypes and especially experimented with the material aiming at a very realistic “feel” of the dummy. Medical assistants regularly tested the new prototypes to evaluate if changing the buttons with the dummy feels comparable to changing the dummy in a “real” belly.

As in this team the members realised different prototypes, coordination work was limited compared to the other teams. There was no need for a clear common goal between the different prototyping teams, but rather the common agreement to work individually on different prototypes and ask others for feedback.

Team Eyeskill / Lazy eye

This careable supports people suffering from the lazy eye syndrome. The careable consists of a virtual reality headset and four cameras. The cameras observe the position of the pupils of each eye, while the user of the headset is passing through a training programme in the virtual reality. According to the pupils' position the training programme is adapted. The team spent time on designing the VR headset in a way that it holds the cameras and is light-tight. The programming team worked on the camera signals. There was also a UX team.

This was the most complex project, due to the high complexity of the software. The complexity made it difficult to efficiently integrate all team members.

Team Vorlesegerät (engl. reader device)

This careable supports people with sight difficulties. The case owner is a young man, whose grandmother suffers from macula degeneration and loses her sight steadily. The careable owner has already started to develop the careable prior to the HACKademy. His aim was to develop an open source text to speech hardware device that “reads” letters from doctors and administrations “aloud”. As the grandmother doesn’t have access to the Internet or mobile devices, the challenge was to realize the Vorlesegerät without mobile phone or WLAN. The first prototype was tested by the grandmother and a person from the German Federation of the Blind and Partially Sighted (DBSV).

More details on the cases can be found online under: <https://beable.info/en/projects/hackademy/>

4.1.2. Evaluation instruments

The HACKademy was evaluated using four different instruments: an online questionnaire was distributed to the participants and filled in by 10

respondents. The main aim of this questionnaire was to learn about the participants' motivation to participate, their expectations and personal benefits, the cooperation in the teams as well as suggestions for improvement.

Complementing interviews were conducted with 4 participants: these interviews focused on personal benefits for participants and the cooperation in the teams and should help to deepen the insights from the questionnaires.

In addition user journey interviews were conducted with 8 participants: The starting point of these interviews was a timeline, where the interviewee was invited to visualize via graphs his/her journey through the co-creation process with regard to aspects like fun or knowledge building. The user journey interviews deepened the understanding of up- and downs in the co-creation process (e.g. why the co-creation process was perceived as enriching on some days but not on others). Examples of user journeys are shown in Figure 1 and 2.

Figure 1: Exemplary user journey 1 HACKademy I

Figure 2: Exemplary user journey 2 HACKademy II

Finally a questionnaire was prepared for the HACKademy facilitators and filled in by 6 persons.

Respondents can be shortly described as following:

Table 4: Participants in the evaluation of HACKademy I

10 Questionnaire participants	Gender: 7 male, 2 female, 1 divers Age: 18-25 y: 2; 25-30 y: 3; 30-40 y: 3; 40-50 y: 1 Profession: 3 designers, 2 IT specialists, 1 engineer, 2 biologists
8 User journey interviews	Gender: 4 male, 4 female
4 Interviews on drivers & barriers	Gender: 4 male Age: 18-25 y: 1; 25-30 y: 1; 30-40 y: 1; 40-50 y: 1 Profession: software engineer, IT student, IT-expert, data engineer
6 facilitator questionnaires	Gender: 2 male, 4 female

4.1.3. Results

In the following chapter we present a summary of the main outcomes from the above mentioned evaluation instruments.

The HACKademy involved a diversified range of participants regarding background knowledge (from experts to newcomers) and expectations (from students wanting to collect credits to careable owners who want to advance with their careable). The HACKademy intended to be an academy to learn about the design thinking process, a place to advance in very short time with the production and documentation of careables; an event where people participated voluntarily and should do what they are interested to do, and a workshop where participants could collect positive experiences by efficiently advancing with their careables and produce first working prototypes. It was difficult to meet all objectives at 100% as they were partly contradicting – e.g. strong voluntary investment and maximum freedom in choosing what one wants to do, contradicts with the affordances of a strict project management to advance with the careables.

Motivation to participate and benefits of the HACKademy I:

The analysis shows that participants had clear expectations and motivational drivers for their involvement in the HACKademy. They can be summarized in four points:

Learn and experience new things:

Learning was one of the main expectations and according to the different profiles of participants they expected to learn different skills; e.g. gaining new skills in the software development, learning how to successfully realise the careable cases, learning hands-on how to use the digital fabrication tools, learning how to use the design thinking approach through its whole process.

Interest in the topic:

Being interested in the topic of digital health in general, or more specifically in one of the topics addressed by the careable cases was another aspect that drove participation in the HACKademy (e.g. a family father participated as he tried to find a solution to the lazy eye syndrome, as half of his family suffered from this syndrome; one developer wanted to support the open source movement)

Succeeding to finish a prototype that supports a good cause:

Completing the prototype was another aspect mentioned, together with the support of a good cause. So participants expected to make something useful, be successful in this task and thus effectively support others who need help.

Getting to know new people and work in a team:

The social aspect of the HACKademy was another driver for participation and also motivational aspect throughout the HACKademy.

A comparison of these initial expectations and drivers with the concrete benefits of the HACKademy, shows that these are closely connected.

Participants reported that they learned to use new software, to apply the design thinking process, and to apply the fab lab tools. They collected rich experiences, also from interacting with the other participants and exchanging knowledge mutually in the teams.

A statement showing this manifold learning opportunities if for example:
„On the one hand I had to train myself in a new programming language for the project – this was an interesting task; for me also to be thrown into this wildly mixed conglomerate of team members, is a cool possibility to experience team dynamics; and to develop the empathy for someone who will never be able to see, is something that one learned.“

Participants were especially **proud**, if they succeeded to have a tangible outcome, a functional prototype as the result of their work.

Here is a statement that describes this aspect: “The best moment? To see and test the new prototype. I saw the new prototype and was surprised how solid it was! There you could really talk about a prototype and not of a „proof of concept“ any more. “

Participants mentioned the **interaction with others** in the very diversified teams and having fun as a result of the work in the teams and the making as such.

Here is a statement for this aspect: „I did some Mock-Up for Saturday, so I was so powerful because of the feedback of the others, I was so satisfied here!“

And they felt motivated to continue their engagement in their groups and/or in the wider maker community

In general, the feedback of participants to the HACKademy was positive, which can be seen in the following statement and also from the answers of participants shown in Figure 3.

“It’s really positive, there is activity. I think I haven’t met such a positive active day or workshop before, I have never felt like this.”

I have achieved something important through this event. | Ich habe etwas Wichtiges durch dieses Event erfahren/erreicht.

10 responses

Alltogether this event was worth taking place. | Es war wert, daran teilgenommen zu haben.

10 responses

Figure 3: General Feedback HACKademy I

Drivers and barriers throughout the event

The analysis above shows that the expectations and outcomes were already quite diversified according to the different profiles of participants. Looking into the experiences of participants throughout the HACKademy, one realizes that these differ strongly too. Depending on the respective team structure, the complexity of prototypes, the own skills and possibilities to contribute, etc. the collaborative work on the careable cases was experienced completely different.

In HACKademy I the teams were provided with input sessions on how to approach their cases from a design thinking perspective, but they were not provided with individual coaches who supported the teams in setting up the production planning and managing the team progress. If the case owners or others took over this role, the team members showed to be much more satisfied with their team work. So it needed a person who voluntarily held the reins.

Another aspect was the complexity of cases and the fact that in some teams expectations were too high for the given time frame and skill set. Thus these expectations needed to gradually be lowered through the HACKademy; an experience which was perceived as not always easy for participants who desired to complete with a functional prototype as compensation for all their work.

A third aspect that influenced participants' experiences was the individual skill set – in general participants felt better, if they could contribute to the team work with their skills and knowledge. If they could not find their ideal “place and role” in the team, two participants reported about a certain frustration and feeling of redundancy, while one said that this left him the freedom to learn from others and experience the nice, relaxed atmosphere.

There was a clear and coherent feedback concerning the timeframe of the HACKademy, which was not perceived as being ideal for many team members. It was difficult to organize the work during the weeks; people lost their motivation to be engaged, lost the connection to their cases due to personal tasks and obligations that captured them as soon as they left the Fablab.

Coherent was also the positive feedback to the organizational team and the coaches that supported the teams when they asked for (see Figure 4).

The support of the coaches at the weekends was very helpful. | Die Unterstützung durch die Coaches am Wochenende war sehr hilfreich.

10 responses

Figure 4: Feedback on the coaches work

Reflective questions for an optimization of the co-creation format

Based on the detailed feedback, there was a set of questions formulated to the organisers of the HACKademy, to reflect on the format and look for the potential of optimization of HACKademy II. These questions were:

- 1 How can teams be more efficiently composed from the very beginning and roles clearer attributed to the participants?
 - Having fun and enjoying the HACKademy is in many cases related to the fact that every participant has a useful contribution to the project and is accepted for this contribution. So it needs the feeling to provide a useful contribution to the group and the overall successful achievement of the group. How can participants be better introduced with regard to their skills and expectations at the beginning of the HACKademy, when the teams are composed?
 - How can participants get a clearer understanding what the careable owner wants to reach in the three weeks, where the focus of work will be and which skills are needed to address the goals?
- 2 How can groups be coordinated?
 - The issue about the role and responsibilities of the group coordinator was apparent in several teams. Is the careable owner ready to take over the role of the group coordinator and does he provide of the necessary skills?
 - Or do coaches take over the task of group coordinators and the case owner is a team member like the others?

- 3 How big should the groups ideally be?
 - Group sizes have been different and it seemed that the smaller groups are easier to organise. Is it therefore better to have smaller groups?
- 4 How can participants have the freedom to work on their solutions, while at the same time being integrated in a clearly defined process?
 - In the HACKademy participants should follow their personal interests, while on the other hand being involved in a complex product development process. Does it make sense to borrow ideas from agile development projects on how to coordinate the development (e.g. regular sprints, team meetings)?
- 5 How can the days in between the week-ends be used? Do they need to be used?
 - During weeks the motivation went down for most of the participants: communication was reduced, tasks not clearly distributed, many participants did not have the time to get involved in the projects. So should weeks be more actively planned and used or is this overloading participants?
- 6 How can participants be better supported at the end of the second week?
 - In all teams the fun and motivation went a bit down in the second week. Either because teams realised that their expectations were too high, or the first load of work was completed and it was not clear how to continue, or things advanced not fast enough. So what would help participants in this phase to keep the motivation high?
- 7 How can the 3D printing process be organised more efficiently?
 - All teams printed around the second weekend, as they all followed the same steps of the design thinking process. Consequently there were waiting times to complete the 3D prints. How can this be better organised?
- 8 How can coaches as well as team members focus on the teamwork only?
 - Coaches and participants need their time to work on their projects, so how can additional activities like cooking be outsourced?
- 9 How can teams be better prepared for potential challenges (intercultural communication, adjustment of expectations, idling time of some team members ...)
 - Does it make sense to address potential challenges at the beginning of the HACKademy and offer potential ways to solve them? Can coaches be better as mediators in the case of conflicts or challenges?

Taking the feedback of HACKademy I into consideration, HACKademy II was re-conceptualised.

4.2. HACKademy II (Agile Heap)

4.2.1. Introduction to HACKademy II

HACKademy II was organised in a summer-school format, with 10 days intensive, uninterrupted work, starting on one week-end and ending on the second week-end.

It took place from the 27th of September to 6th of October 2019, in In the workshops of the Technical University Berlin and partly also the Makerspace of [CADUS e.V.](#) There were three case providers this time and 20 participants joined the event.

In HACKademy II the individual teams had their own coach each, who was there to support the communication between team members and to guide the organizational tasks of structuring, planning and controlling all the activities throughout the prototyping process. The teams were requested to use the tool of daily “check-ins” and “check-outs” from agile development processes, where the members meet one time in the morning to get a quick overview of the daily tasks and one time in the evening to report back to the whole team how everybody advanced. Again, the first week-end was dedicated to an introduction and the application of the design thinking process. During the week the teams were encouraged to work at their own pace on the prototypes; input sessions were offered to all teams in this period as well, but to a much lower extend. The last week-end was dedicated to documentation of the project in the careables welder app, the production of a short video, and the final presentation of the work.

All together the event involved the following participants numbers:

Table 5: Participants In HACKademy II

HACKademy II	At the Open Health HACKademy, three interdisciplinary teams jointly developed careables.	27.09. - 06.10.2019	20 participants
HACKademy II Meet Up I	Talks and Testing Prototypes with interested guests after first design sprint	28.09.2019	45 participants

HACKademy II Meet Up II	Accompanying Public final presentation and Testing of final Prototype	06.10.2019	60 participants
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The three cases of the HACKademy II were:

Team Footbike:

The team footbike worked 10 days on the creation of Svens bike. Due to Svens spasticity the bike needed disability-related adjustments, with the biggest challenge being to make it possible to brake with his feet. Sven wanted to ride a recumbent bike and thus the team constellation, mixed of a designer and an engineer with welding skills and two team members with medical and organizational expertise was ideal to reach his goal.

Team E-Scooter for wheelchair users:

The scooter team worked on the idea to develop a system that secures wheelchairs on an e-scooter. E-scooters seemed to Alina, the case owner, a practical little means of transport, that could offer to wheelchair users to be more mobile, free and could easily get additional power. Also the fun factor seemed tempting. Alina could only take part the first three days of the HACKademy; the team felt that it would have benefitted from a longer involvement.

Team Joystick:

Team Joystick aimed at developing a joystick for power wheelchairs, that can be operated intuitively and blindly when needed (for example under tables) and fits the requirements of different hands and uses. Jonas, the case owner, uses a power wheel chair since childhood and always wondered why they are so unergonomic and rigid to control. The starting point is a joystick similar to a gamepad. With more buttons in different positions, an ergonomic handle and a holder that offers more flexibility. But this was also the most complex case, that needed not only good design skills to model the joystick, but also deep programming skills to control the power wheelchair, which is as such a closed system. Jonas could not take part in the whole HACKademy, and the biggest challenge of the team constellation was a missing IT expert.

More details on the cases can be found online under: <https://be-able.info/en/projects/hackademy/>

4.2.2. Evaluation instruments

The HACKademy II was evaluated using three different instruments comparable to HACKademy I: the online questionnaire to participants, the online questionnaire to facilitators and the user journey interviews with participants. This time there were no additional interviews conducted with regard to motivational drivers and benefits, to avoid overloading respondents. These questions were covered in the user journey interviews and the questionnaires. An example for a user journey can be seen in the following figure 5.

Figure 5: Exemplary user journey HACKademy II

Respondents can be shortly described as following:

Table 6: Participants in the evaluation of HACKademy II

8 Questionnaire participants	Gender: 2 male, 6 female Age: 18-25 y: 1; 25-30 y: 1; 30-40 y: 6; Profession: 3 designers, 1 engineer, 1 computer science, 1 doctor, 1 occupational therapist, 1 unemployed
8 User journey interviews	Gender: 4 male, 4 female
8 facilitators questionnaires	Gender: 4 male, 4 female

4.2.3. Results:

HACKademy II had the same claim as HACKAdemy I: to be an event where participants with diversified backgrounds and skills can learn new things related to digital fabrication and healthcare, while completing a functional careable prototype for the case owners in a very short period of 10 days. The fact that this is a challenging format for organisers and participants alike did not change in HACKademy II. What changed compared to HACKademy I was the new format of 10 days, which was better accepted by participants; and the supportive role of team coaches, which made the work in two of the three teams a great experience for those involved.

In the following paragraphs the main results from the evaluation of HACKademy II are presented. Again it starts with the motivation for participation and the concrete benefits for participants, before it presents the challenges and drivers that were experienced throughout the HACKademy II. This section concludes with lessons learned and recommendations for HACKademy III, which is planned for summer 2020.

Motivation to participate and benefits of the HACKademy II:

The main motivational driver was **learning**: Learning new skills (maker, project management, design), learning how to apply the design thinking process in the „real world“, learning how people from other disciplines address the challenge of producing the prototypes - e.g. a designer who wishes to understand how engineers or technicians solve the problem, while an engineer aims to change perspectives and better understand how designers work.

Learning was closely related to the work in the team and the **networking aspect**, which was the second most important driver to participate in the HackAdemy too. As can be seen below the teamwork was also an important motivational aspect throughout the whole runtime of the HackAdemy.

A very specific aspect of networking was mentioned by one interviewee: He/she was looking for a job and hoped that he/she would get to know other engineers in the event to whom he/she could demonstrate his skills and thus get a job opportunity.

Of course all interviewees were interested in the aspect of **making and DIY**, but there was one maker who specifically said that this love for making was the main driver of participation. Finding solutions to a problem is what is the most challenging and fun part to this interviewee and the reason to participate.

The fact that learning, networking and making also resulted in **helping somebody** else was an extra value of the HACKademy, and made people feel good. But it was not the main motivation to participate, except for the case owners and one

participant: this interviewee knows from own experiences that classical health devices are often of no use and thus it requires taking matters into one's own hands.

For one case owner the work with the be-able/careable organisation team was another driver, as he liked the spirit of the be-able team.

A comparison of expectations and motivations to participate with the concrete benefits shows again a strong connection:

Learning was the most important motivation to participate and also an important benefit experienced by all participants. They learned how to apply the design thinking process in a practical context, they learned from others (especially when they had a strong expertise in certain tasks), they learned from the coaches. Learning was related to design thinking and fabrication skills but also to team management processes.

Another important benefit mentioned by almost all interviewees was the **pleasure to work in the teams** and get to know new and nice people. As this teamwork was such an important driver and benefit, none of the interviewees felt very much intrigued by the idea of organising the collaborative creation of careables remotely.

There was the **pleasure of making**, of working on the prototypes. And finally the important **feeling of success**, having successfully completed the challenging task of constructing the careables and having a prototype that is useful to the case owners.

In a next step, the perceived problems throughout the new format of the HACKademy II and also the positive drivers that helped participants to overcome the barriers and keep their engagement high, are introduced. This part was especially interesting for the organisers to see in how far the new format changed the participants' journey in the HACKademy II.

Challenges throughout the event:

The case as a challenge:

All teams perceived the objective of finishing their prototypes within 10 days as a main challenge. They experienced that the creation of the prototypes was more complex than they initially thought. It was difficult to set feasible objectives, also given the fact that all teams wanted to create something great in these 10 days. So all teams experienced a continuous flow of up- and downs during the construction process: having an idea on how to address a problem and feeling good, trying it out, and realising that it worked (feeling extremely good) or contrary did not work or needed even more adaptations (feeling frustrated).

The Joystick team had a very complex case that would have needed a narrowing down of expectations and objectives from the very beginning. The prototype was too complex to build as a whole in the 10 days, thus the team members were disappointed at the end of the HACKademy, as they missed this highly engaging feeling of success at the end of their involvement.

Teamwork:

The teamwork was perceived as very rewarding and worked well in two of the three teams.

The third team experienced considerable challenges in their teamwork, but they were also the ones with the most complex prototype. They had to deal with several problems: 1) team members left already at the beginning of the HACKademy, urging the others to rearrange the tasks. 2) the team missed the expertise of a technician or programmer, who would have been a prerequisite to complete the prototype. The rest of the team tried to make themselves acquainted with the programming task during the HACKademy, but this was not only time consuming but also insufficient to complete the prototype. 3) the complexity of the prototype complicated the planning of team activities. Every team member had another imagination what should be the outcome of their work; they set themselves too high objectives at the beginning of the HACKademy, given the limited timeframe and skill set and needed to rearrange this expectations in the course of the event.

Agenda and course of events:

There was diversified feedback concerning the agenda of the HACKademy: For some the first two days stuffed with design thinking exercises were highly interesting, as they loved to apply the design thinking process in this setting; for others, who wanted to mainly work on the prototypes and get them ready, these two days were too long and not efficient enough.

For some participants the input sessions during the week were just right, others would have loved to have the whole week for working on the prototypes only. But even amongst those, who felt rather disturbed by the input sessions, there was positive feedback if the input session addressed a topic that was specifically relevant for the construction of their prototypes. The documentation session was perceived as specifically critical, as several participants would have preferred to continue the work on their prototypes instead of getting involved in the documentation.

There was also one interviewee, who clearly stated that the video-shooting and photo-shooting during the week was perceived as too disruptive.

Learning and skills:

In one team, members had to acquire the necessary knowledge to take over some technical tasks. This learning was perceived as an interesting challenge, if it was done in a team and supported by one of the coaches. But it was perceived as a burden when it was conducted alone. Then participants felt a sense of being overburdened and ashamed of not supporting the team.

Only two participants felt that they could not fully integrate their expertise; They thought that they acted as consultants only.

Drivers in the process:

After the discussion of problems in the previous paragraphs, the following paragraphs introduce the facts that were perceived as motivating during the HACKademy or a means to overcome the problems discussed before.

Flow of the team:

Especially members of the two “successful” teams stressed the important motivational factor of the team work. They said that in times of setbacks, when things turned out to be more complicated than expected, the collaborative activities of setting up a new plan together, dividing new tasks, and starting to work again, brought confidence. Motivating were also the check-outs in the evening, when the teams realised how much they accomplished together and that, even when one did not advance, others in the team advanced. Team members mutually pushed each other through difficult phases.

It was perceived as a good feeling when different skills and expertise in the group complemented one another, so that one could take responsibility and play a part the group, and knowledge “overlaps” between team members helped to understand each other.

Coaches and Organisers:

Respondents described the attentiveness of the organisers who showed a strong interest in the well-being of their participants and helped out whenever needed. Generally the coaches were perceived as having a very important role in the whole production process. In two cases they helped to keep an overview of all activities and structure the work. The team of organisers held everything together and showed responsible for the positive, innovative atmosphere of the HACKAdemy.

Agenda:

Concerning the overall agenda of the HACKademy, positive aspects that interviewees mentioned were:

- The agenda point, when the teams provided feedback to the other teams
- The structure of the HACKademy: the activities in the beginning appeared less important but turned out to be important at the end (this comes from an engineer).
- The freedom to work on the projects (without specific input sessions)
- The freedom to do follow own interests and ideas. This interviewee mentioned that he had the freedom to chose between trying out own ideas - everybody would encourage him to do so - and supporting others in trying out there ideas.
- The freedom to move freely between rooms, workshops etc.

- The continuous availability of instruments

The co-design with case owners:

The co-design of the prototypes together with the case owners was an enriching experience which helped to understand the requirements during the development process, e.g. how connected a wheelchair user is with his wheel chair and that he would not like to fulfil certain move. It was also an important motivational factor to have the person, who will benefit from the developed careable, on the spot.

General comments and suggestions for improvement:

Finally, participants provided some more general comments and suggestions for improvement, which can be summarized as follows:

Time:

10 days were long, but nearly too short to complete the prototypes. Participants said that they would not have committed to participating in the HACKademy II if it would have taken longer, so it seems that the timely setting was much better than in HACKademy I.

More participants/more organisations etc.:

Respondents said that it would have been great to share this experience with more participants. They suggested trying to involve more organisations, maybe cooperate with schools, and continue activities like the participation at the maker faire. They suggested using other Hackathons to promote the HACKademy also amongst real talented programmers. There was the suggestion to cooperate with related projects in the field and to approach schools for occupational therapists.

Cancel cases in time:

There was a suggestion to cancel the prototyping of a careable in advance, if the organisational team realised already during the setting up of the HACKademy that the project was either too complicated to realise within 10 days or the allocated team missed the right competences to realise the specific project.

Reduce interruptions:

Several interviewees suggested reducing “on-top” tasks and avoid interrupting the flow of the teams (e.g. by photo and video taking session)

Have a free Sunday afternoon:

Two team members suggested finishing earlier on the first Sunday and “force” HACKAdemy members to take a rest.

Face-to-face:

All interviewees stressed the importance of the “face-to-face” setting of the HACKademy as an important motivational factor but also a setting that supports mutual learning and the pleasure to take part in such a co-creation process. This face-to-face event introduces the topic of making in the health area. One would not have the idea to participate in a case without this character of an event.

4.3. Health&Care Summer School (OpenDot)

4.3.1. Introduction to the OpenDot Health&Care Summer School

The OpenDot Health & Care Summer School borrowed from the concept of the first HACKademy. It was an event organized by OpenDot in Milan, during two week-ends (8th-9th of June 2019 and 22nd to 23rd of June 2019) and offered an intensive training course of 2 weeks about design for care in cooperation with “DDMP – Distributed Design Market Platform”. Before the event, OpenDot organized a call for needs, which resulted in 3 cases, that were selected for the Summer School. Comparable to the HACKademy in Berlin, the agenda of the Summer School foresaw a series of input sessions from internal and external speakers, as well as group works to gain hands-on experiences on the DIY fabrication by working on the three cases. The time in between the weekends was planned as a time, where the teams could work independently on their prototypes. All together the OpenDot Health&Care Summer School had the following participants (see table 7):

Table 7: Participants in the OpenDot Health&Care Summer School

Health& Care Summer school - Open talk	The opentalk titled “Innovation in healthcare by design and empathy” had 4 special guests. The main topic was design for empathy presenting 3 different case studies which imply the use of technologies and the co-design approach.	7.6.2019	30 participants
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Health&Care Summer School	The Health&Care Summer School focuses on "Design for care" with the aim of developing concrete and simple solutions for the needs of people with disabilities.	8-9.6. and 22.-23.6. 2019	14 participants
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The Open Dot Health & Care Summer school had three cases:

Team Music:

The music team worked on a musical instrument for David. David suffers from cerebral palsy and has a motoric disability. He starts secondary school in September 2019 and would love to have a tool that can be used during the music lessons.

Team Learning:

Team learning worked together with Pamela, a speech therapist. In her work she experienced that more and more children have difficulties with arithmetic calculations. That's why she invented a pair of gloves that allows children with dyscalculia to learn, understand and memorize mathematical tables. She needed support in now producing the gloves.

Team sport:

Team sport worked together with Rosina. The 31-year-old woman, who has been suffers for about two years from a disability, an incomplete tetraplegia for which she has difficulty moving her hands. She loves rowing, which helps her a lot, but does not have the strenghts in flexion in her hands. That's why she worked with her team on a mechanisme to support her in rowing.

More information on the cases can be found online under: <https://www.opendotlab.it/portfolio-item/healthcare-summer-school/>

4.3.2. Evaluation instruments

An online questionnaire was distributed to the participants at the end of the summer school. It contained 4 question blocks: the first block embraced questions that helped to better understand motivational drivers for participation in the summer school and collect formative feedback on the format, length, content etc. The second block focused on the co-creation process and the teamwork. The third block aimed to support a better understanding about the

personal gains and benefits of the respondents' participation in the summer school, while the last question block collected socio-demographic data from the respondents.

The questionnaire was set up via google-forms and invitations to participate in the survey were distributed by OpenDot to the participants via email. The analysis and summarization of survey results was conducted by the ZSI evaluation team.

Respondents can be shortly described as following:

Table 8: Participants in the evaluation of the Health&Care Summer School

9 Questionnaire participants	Gender: 2 male, 6 female, 1 divers Age: 18-25 y: 4; 26-35 y: 5; Profession: 6 designers, 2 students
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4.3.3. Results

This chapter presents the results from the analysis of questionnaire responses. As it can be seen the expectations and motivation to participate as well as the concrete benefits are comparable to what we found in the HACKademy.

Expectations

The participants' initial expectations towards their involvement to the summer school were mainly related to learning and meeting and exchanging with others. Participants mentioned:

- Learning about healthcare and digital fabrication
- Learning the co-design process and how to create empathy in this process
- Meeting professionals and interesting people to share knowledge and work in a team
- Helping the careable owners in their everyday lives
- Facing a new challenge

Motivation:

The answers revealed two main motivations for participations: 1) the acquisition of knowledge, and 2) the aspect of creating something that meets real needs.

Aspects under 1) were: learning how to do the co-creation, how to create health care projects and get to know more about the maker world

Aspects under 2) were: trying to solve an actual problem, working for real user needs, really making a difference, making something that is used in real life responding to needs

Personal benefits:

There were two important benefits from the SummerSchool that were mentioned by the participants: The first one was **learning new skills** about the work with digital fabrication tools, the co-design process, and prototyping (6 mentions); the second one the fact to **meet new, interested people** (5 mentions).

“Networking: i met amazing people, really helpful during the project and able to create the right atmosphere where to work; Skills: i learned a lot about how to manage the co-design session, problems, digital fabrication and the prototype phase. Finally i believe that healthcare is a wonderful sector where the DF can be applied and this kind of summer school is a big value for the community.”

Altogether the SummerSchool was a positive experience for participants. The statement “I achieved something important through this event” was rated with a mean value of 5,2 (on a 6 point-likert scale from 1=not at all to 6=very much). And the statement “Altogether this event was worth taking place” had even better ratings with a mean value of 5,4 (on a 6 point-likert scale from 1=not at all to 6=very much).

This positive experience was also reflected in positive statements concerning the Summer School.

“I really suggest this experience to everyone because it's a good examples of good co-working and co-design with people and I really like the fablab environment.”

Interesting was again the feedback on the format as such and what participants experienced throughout the event.

Timing and organizational aspects:

The time of the summer school was perceived by a majority of respondents (6) too short and by only two as just perfect.

In a set of questions concerning the organizational settings, the locations and lectures received very positive ratings. Timing still was rated satisfactorily but to a lower extent (see figure 6).

Figure 6: Satisfaction with organizational aspects of the SummerSchool

Further ratings show that the “support to develop the solution” and the “information about the specific healthcare cases” was rated as highly satisfactorily, while the “clearness of the objectives of the summer school” received a bit lower ratings (see figure 7).

Figure 7: Satisfaction with support and information provided

Challenges in the teamwork:

The biggest challenge faced in the team, was the missing availability of all team members especially during the week, as some of them lived in distant places and others were not available due to other duties and businesses.

Other challenges mentioned were the lack of knowledge about some design skills and the hard work during the design and the fabrication process.

The question about **what worked well** in the teams showed quiet homogenous answers. Several respondents mentioned that the different skills and experiences of the participants greatly supported the realization of the prototypes.

One mentioned the positive experience of overcoming problems and difficulties arriving at a good solution, another one mentioned the good communication and availability of his team mates.

The closed questions concerning the teamwork showed that the most difficult task was the “independent work on tasks during the week” followed by tasks of “structuring the teamwork” and “always knowing how to contribute”.

The co-design process was rated as a very satisfactory instrument to support the team at work (see figures 8 and 9).

Also, in an open-ended question related to the usefulness of the co-design process the feedback was all positive, like:

“It has been a great instrument to create a common language between the participants.”

Figure 8: Collaboration in the SummerSchool I

Figure 9: Collaboration in the SummerSchool II

What participants liked most about the Summer School was

- the team and support of OpenDot,
- the co-design sessions and the fact to respond to real users needs, meeting them personally, and
- the work with motivated people.

What participants liked least was

- the short time available and
- the high workload for this short time, which became especially difficult when
- group members were not skilled enough, have problems to communicate in English or are not available.

Suggestions for improvement turned mainly around the fact to better inform participants about the required availability and skills and also select them accordingly, only if they are available, live nearby, speak English and provide of the required technical skills.

4.4. MakeHealth: Prototyping series (WAAG)

4.4.1. Introduction to the MakeHealth Prototyping series

There were two MakeHealth Prototyping series organized by WAAG in 2018. They aimed to introduce interested makers, healthcare providers and people with special needs to the DIY co-creation process and support the making and documentation of careables prototypes over a series of events that always took place on weekends. Diversified teams were supported by maker competences and guidance in how to come to their solution. The testing of this format resulted in detailed insights into how to set up the co-creation process and what to consider when facilitating this process over a period of around 2 and a half months. These lessons learned were documented in detail in Deliverable “D1.2. Training Kit: On prototyping series for healthcare innovation”.

Altogether the following events were organized as part of series 1 and 2:

Table 9: Participants in the MakeHealth Prototyping series

Event name	Description	Date	Participants
Made 4 You series 1.1	Co-creation and co.design sessions based on the open call launched by Waag	17.5.2018	16
Made 4 You series 1.2		24.5.2018	12
Made 4 You series 1.3		05.6.2018	12
Made 4 You series 1.4		07.6.2018	12
Made 4 You series 1.5		14.6.2018	12
Made 4 You series 1.6		21.6.2018	12
Made 4 You series 1.7		28.6.2018	12
Made 4 You series 1.8		05.7.2018	12
Made 4 You series 2.1		22.09.2018	12
Made 4 You series 2.2		29.09.2018	12
Made 4 You series 2.3		06.10.2018	12
Made 4 You series 2.4		20.10.2018	12
Made 4 You series 2.5		03.11.2018	12
Made 4 You series 2.6		10.11.2018	12

Following are some of the careables, which have been worked upon in the two prototyping series:

Stomanoir

The Stomanoir supports Ostomates in their hygiene care by providing a sanitary solution to personal inconveniences. The team wanted to find a method to eliminate unpleasant odours when depositing a used stoma bag in the trash can. The solution was found by producing silicone caps to attach to the stoma bag and in doing so, locking-in odours before they can escape. The next challenge was to make the caps from biodegradable materials. Specifically for urostomies, a disposable sticker was produced to secure urine odours from seeping. Additionally, they manufactured an innovative travel bag, providing the Ostomate with a portable toilet if/where necessary.

Quali-fire

The team wanted to find a way to monitor the symptoms of Multiple Sclerosis (MS) as a way to investigate what could be possible external markers of inflammation, in order to help people with MS manage and understand the causes of inflammation. This speculative project aimed to use automated measurement to better understand the causes of inflammation, thereby helping to reduce external factors in daily life and manage disease progression. Measurements include a CPR blood test to indicate inflammation, an infrared sensor to record continuous temperature measurement and a wearable device that registers the frequency of spasms and muscle stiffness. The project brings together qualitative and quantitative data to provide valuable information about environmental factors which could promote inflammation and potentially disease progression.

Squeeze-a-ball

Squeeze-a-ball is a knitted pressure sensor wrapped in a knitted anti-stress ball hooked up to a tablet computer. People can squeeze the ball whenever they experience pain, and the amount of force indicates their pain level. The squeeze force will be recorded and visualised in a tablet application, both real-time and as a pain diary.

By making pain measurement less intrusive, patient-initiated, and capable of real-time monitoring, Squeeze-a-ball can improve the clinical reaction to pain, improve the scientific understanding of pain, and provide biofeedback-based distraction for the patient. This prototype was developed in MakeHealth session one, and further developed in session two.

A room shoe

Falling down at home is a major cause of fatalities and requiring long-term care for elderly people. There are several causes for falling down, however in this project, the team focused on the friction between shoes and flooring since elderly people tend to drag their feet along the flooring. According to literature, there is a safety range of friction coefficient which prevents falling down. In

order to maintain the safe friction range, a room shoe features a felt outsole, is lightweight, and has an ankle strap developed based on friction testing between some outsole materials and some floorings.

Pimp my cane

Debby lives in Amsterdam, and she is visually impaired. She was overlooked by a car and got hit. By enhancing the visibility for visually impaired people by means of light emitting white canes, Jedi style, this could be prevented. So she started experimenting together with a team and made a shiny sextopus, and Debby fumbled with thrash and flashlights. Her brother gave her prepared reflecting sticks, and another team member made the 3D printed pieces that can hold a flashlight. Together they will continue developing the canes and later this year they will launch a campaign to share the cane open source and ready to use. This prototype was developed in MakeHealth session one, and further developed in session two

BruxHack

The BruxHack is a night-time wearable that aims to stop you from grinding your teeth and clenching your jaws, a condition known as bruxism. They chose an eye-covering, sleep mask-like design. It has an integrated Near-Infrared Spectroscopy (NIRS) which measures the oxygenation of the masseter muscle, as well as a Transcutane Electric Neuro Stimulator (TENS) which stimulates the nerve to the masseter muscle, thereby ensuring muscle relaxation without being noticeable. The current version is an early prototype that yet needs to be experimentally tested on both effectiveness and usability.

4.4.2. Evaluation instruments

An online questionnaire was distributed to the participants at the end of the second MakeHealth: prototyping series. It contained one question block about the initial expectations towards ones involvement, one question block that examined the perceived benefits from the involvement, questions that collected formative feedback on the prototyping series and investigated the work in teams, and a final one that collected socio-demographic data.

The questionnaire was set up in Typeform, an online platform for questionnaires, invitations to participate in the survey were distributed by the WAAG society to the participants via email. The responses were translated from Dutch to English and analysed and summarized by the ZSI evaluation team.

Respondents can be shortly described as following:

Table 10: Participants in the evaluation of the MakeHealth Prototyping series

14 Questionnaire participants	Gender: 4 male, 10 female Age: 18-25 y: 2; 26-35 y: 4; 36-45 y: 1; 46-55 y: 2;
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	56-65 y: 4; above 65: 1; Background (multiple answers possible): 6 designers, 4 students, 3 health care professionals, 2 technicians, 2 user experience experts, 1 PhD student
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Socio-demographic data are also visualized in the following two graphs (figure 10 and 11):

Figure 10: Age group of people involved in the evaluation

Asked about their background, we see that most respondents indicate being designers and/or makers. But we also have three health professionals in the group of respondents.

Figure 11: Background of people involved in the evaluation

4.4.3. Results

Initial expectations and how we met them

The first questions touched upon the initial motivation of participants to be involved in the MakeHealth prototyping series. Answers were diverse in this regard and show also how many expectations this format needed to address.

- There were first those participants, who wanted to use the co-design sessions as a way to further develop their ideas. (“Frame an idea; share idea and get support for my idea.”)
- Then there were participants who were interested in the aspect of collaborative creation, driven by the wish to contribute to the creation of a great solution was. (“Collaboratively design & make great solutions for challenges in healthcare.”)
- Related to that is the aspect of getting to know new people and learning from each other. (“Expected to get in contact with nice people, with nice ideas and develop practical solutions for real questions.”)
- As well as getting insights into the design process and how to conduct user-driven design, especially with people with healthcare questions.

When respondents were subsequently asked if the MakeHealth prototyping series met their initial expectations, the answers were to a large extent positive (see figure 12).

Figure 12: Meeting participants' expectations

Also the rating of the prototyping series was positive (see figure 13).

Figure 13: Rating of the prototyping series

When respondents were asked for an explanation for their rating the following reasons were provided:

- the fact to team up with other people and work on real solutions
- the educational, inspiring input from the workshops
- The well organized and structured sessions and the good support provided to the participants.

Original statements are:

"I'm really happy with the sessions, initiatives that put efforts for makers, and see the importance of concepts that are still in development."

"People with a real, practical healthcare related problem, or likes an idea to team up with other people, is able to develop and explore solutions. With a bit of luck there is a working prototype possible."

But there was also one feedback that required for more support in the second series:

"I learned a lot the first series. Second series: I had the feeling that there was less support available and hoped to be further in development of my ideas. But this can come..."

Personal outcomes

Comparing the initial expectations with the concrete benefits of the prototyping series, there are again close connections. Respondents that outcomes were:

- the prototypes themselves or the ideas generated during the prototyping sessions

- a knowledge increase with regard to the usage of the machines, the design thinking and group moderation processes, programming.
- First experiences with the co-design process
- Being surrounded by positive people

The next questions served to get formative feedback on the format as such and learn about the problems encountered or positive experiences:

The quantitative question about the satisfaction of users with different aspects of the prototyping series shows that respondents were most satisfied with the tutors and the available knowledge, but in general the rating was very positive (see figure 14).

Figure 14: Satisfaction with the prototyping series

Teamwork

Respondents' teamwork was perceived generally as well structured and teams worked well together (see figure 15).

Figure 15: Collaboration in the prototyping series

The biggest challenges of the teamwork were:

- keeping the focus, sticking to the agreements, keeping the commitment until the end of the project.
- limited available time of the team members.
- finding the right material, designing an object in compact shape or coding.
- documenting the lessons learned and failures
- physical limitations, like Parkinson tremors, that challenged the teamwork.

When asked what worked particularly well in the teams, answers highlighted:

- the multidisciplinary approach, the different knowledge that came together and the good, enthusiastic team spirit to find solutions together.
- the support of the workshop facilitators
- fixed time schedules, a clear task division and the person with the health care question in lead

To understand a longer-term effect, respondents were asked how they want to follow up on the MakeHealth prototyping series. Many respondents stated that they

- wanted to continue their work on their existing or new prototypes.

Additional aspects were

- being informed about upcoming prototyping events or
- to have a similar makerspace where healthcare solutions are offered to people with specific needs.

Recommendations and comments

Finally respondents were asked for their recommendations and comments:

The final comments from participants were mostly very positive like:

- *“Keep going. It is a practical and useful co-create programme. It made people's dream come true.”*
- *“You guys were great! I found it a fantastic and unique event. Go for a structural network /makerspace.”*

But there were **also concrete suggestions for improvement** like:

- *“The meetups could be spread in time and have more challenges”*
- *“One thing to improve Make Health is to organise more mixed teams in which all needed expertise is present, and at the beginning of the workshop series do some more exercises to learn to collaborate.”*
- *“There is a difference between the first time I participated and the second. To really develop your idea, you need to have more team disciplines and time to really develop a working prototype”*

5. Evaluation of the careables and welder platform

The careable and welder platform has been developed in close cooperation with users from different stakeholder groups and has so far run through two versions. The first version was developed at the beginning of the project and then redesigned and improved, resulting in a version, that was launched in October 2019. The process and user involvement that led to this version 2 is documented in more detail in the Deliverable D3.2.

Relevant for this document is a broader user acceptance testing that involves end-users from Italy, Austria, Germany and the Netherlands to test the version 2 of the platforms and is organized at the time of writing this report. This user acceptance testing focuses on the aspects of usability and perceived usefulness. Two scenarios were created in German, English and Italian language. In these scenarios test-users are invited to run through four pre-defined tasks on our platform and provide feedback on the ease of use and usefulness of the careable platforms for fulfilling these tasks using feedback cards. The tasks themselves focus on the main features of the platform: finding and sharing careables, looking for resources or events; and specifically investigates the switch between the careables general platform and the welder app with all the documented careable products. Next to tasks and feedback cards, the user acceptance testing contains a general usability questionnaire

and a set of questions on perceived usefulness and suggestions for improvement for a final discussion with the test users.

One scenario and an example of a task is shown in the following 4 figures (figures 16-19). At the time of finalizing this report 10 user tests have been conducted. The analysis and summary of these tests will help to optimize the platforms before the launch in 01/2020 and be summarized in the Deliverable 4.3.

Scenario1: Martin is 33 years old and lives with his girlfriend in Milano. He had an accident when he was a child and is a wheelchair user since then. With his physical limitations he lives an active life, working and following his hobbies. He experienced, that this independent life with a wheelchair in Milano often requires a certain inventiveness and flexibility.

Now he heard about the platform „careables“. There, other wheelchair users share their ideas and solution on how to facilitate their lives. He wants to take a look at that.

 Careables.org is managed by the Made4You project and has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 780298.

Figure 16: One scenario for the user-acceptance testing

Situation 1: Look up practical solutions for wheelchair users

- Martin would like to find self-made solutions and products, which facilitate the lives of other wheelchair users.
- He accesses www.careables.org.

Which careables for wheelchair users can you find there?
Please help him to find that out.

Figure 17: Task 1 of a testing scenario

FEEDBACK CARD – Situation 1

How did you feel, when trying out the suggested situation on the careables platform? (Please tick the most appropriate symbol)

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How difficult or easy was it for you to successfully solve the suggested situation? (Please tick the most appropriate box)

<input type="checkbox"/>				
Very difficult		neither/nor		Very easy

How satisfied are you with the features that the careables platform offered you to solve the suggested situation?

<input type="checkbox"/>				
Very unsatisfied		neither/nor		Very satisfied

How would you rate the time that you needed to solve the suggested situation?

<input type="checkbox"/>				
Needed too much time		neither/nor		Needed only a short time

What I liked....

What I didn't like

Ideas, suggestions, improvements ...

Figure 18: Feedback card for task 1

**GENERAL Feedback on
the careables platform**

(Please tick the most appropriate box)

	Fully disagree		neither/nor		Fully agree
• I think that I would like to use this system frequently.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
• I found the system unnecessarily complex.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
• I thought the system was easy to use.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
• I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this system.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
• I found the various functions in this system were well integrated.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
• I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
• I would imagine that most people would learn to use this system very quickly.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
• I found the system very cumbersome to use.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
• I felt very confident using the system.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
• I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system.	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Figure 19: Usability questionnaire

Although the project continually works on the improvement of the careable and welder app, users could already have access to it in the previous months. The project has not yet specifically promoted the platform in its stakeholder communities, nevertheless access statistics provide a first impression about what appears important to the user.

In the last three months starting with beginning of October to 19th of December 2019, the careables platform www.careables.org had 3,333 visitors. Details can be seen in Figure 20.

Figure 20: User access to careables.org

Important pages next to the landing page are:

- About the project,
- Discover Careables,
- Stories and
- Resources.
- Also some news got a lot of attention, like the Exiii Hackberry Myo Electric Prosthetic Arm and the Medica World Forum for Medicine in Düsseldorf.

We had 2,850 visitors to the Welder app and a number of 45,000 page views on welder.

At the moment we count 105 careables on the welder platform.

6. careables potential impact on Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

Social innovation policies, including the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) aim at lowering or discarding the barriers preventing from full participation in political, economic, and social life. This is also in line with the careables objectives. Thus, we are outlining how the results of the careables project may contribute to achieving the SDGs. It should be noted however, that the SDG indicators are rooted in the context of international development work and, consequently designed towards very specific measure in the developmental context. While these measures are directly aligned with the careables objectives we can identify some contributions to achieving the SDGs.

As a first step in this process we identified the SDG goals and specific targets where careables has the potential to contribute. In a close examination of the SDG goals and careables expected outcomes, it is surprising to see that we not only contribute to goal 3, good health and wellbeing, but also to complementary goals that are more on responsible production and consumption, new modes of manufacturing and equality. The following image (Figure 21) relates careables outcomes to SDG goals and targets.

Figure 21: SDG mapping

In order to bring evidence for the careables contribution we have identified a list of indicators amongst those already presented in Deliverable D4.1 and corresponding impact measures (Figure 22 below). In the context of this project we should see these indicators rather in a qualitative manner and consider e.g. the quality of life improvements on individual stories and personal trajectories.

careables contribution	indicators	impact measures
Support access to health-care for all	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accessibility of the platform 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • W3C & WCAG compliance
Support inclusive & sustainable production of health-care products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Usability of careables platform and documentation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Usability (e.g. readability, ease of navigation, usefulness)
Increase access to and skills for digital fabrication technology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Replicability of careables 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • User experience (e.g. stimulation, novelty)
Support inclusion and empowerment of people with disability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Effectiveness of careables training activities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Full documentation of formats • Communication about formats
Support Global South countries in responsible consumption and production of health-care products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improve quality of life of people with special needs (according to WHO dimensions) • Uptake of careables practices by GIG partners in the Global South 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improvement of documentation • Documentation of replications • Feedback from training events • Documented outcomes/products from training activities • Social relationships of careables users • Emotional functioning of careables users • Physical functioning of careables users • careables produced and replicated by GIG partners

Figure 22: Indicators for careables SDG contributions

Currently, we have indications about the usability, use experience, feedback from the training events and individual stories from careables users. Sven's story is e.g. a perfect example of how a careables can empower an individual and improve their quality of life. In the final report (Deliverable D4.3) we will provide further evidence on these indicators and summarize the main impact findings.

7. Summary, conclusions and outlook

By offering different formats of co-creation in different European countries, the project learned that trans-disciplinary, compiled teams of citizens with different skills, expectations, age groups and social backgrounds can successfully co-create careables that address very specific needs of people who suffer from disabilities or illness. We learned that the diversity of motivational drivers of participants is also reflected in the multitude of benefits that they take from their participation: Learning is one of the most important benefits and takes place in all forms (learning through input session, hands-on trying, observing of others, exploring together); it covers skills like digital fabrication, design thinking, project management, group moderation, but also individual characteristics like empathy, and resilience.

Collaboration and the pleasure coming from the work in teams is another benefit, together with the creation of new personal relationships within and across the teams.

The joy of succeeding after a series of ups and downs in the co-creation process is a third benefit, experienced in all our co-creation formats. Participants felt satisfied that they were able to contribute to a good cause.

Finally, the sessions also helped to demonstrate that taking health and care aspects into their own hands can result in a valuable product – thus a certain feeling of empowerment was shared by participants.

Comparing these benefits with the objectives set out by the project shows that we successfully address objective 2 and 3 with our co-creation formats (see Figure 23). Informal talks with case providers also confirm contributions to their improved quality of life (see objective 5 in figure 23). This aspect needs to be followed up closely however in the final project year and we need to collect more evidence for such claims, e.g. via interviews with the case holders.

Ranking of careables objectives

Figure 23: Supporting objective 2,3 and 5 via the co-creation formats

To reach the noted effects intense learning and reflection within the careables team took place on how to best facilitate the co-creation process of careables. We identified the main barriers of involving diversified stakeholder groups in the co-creation process and explored how to approach these barriers.

From the HACKademy we learned that an educational co-creation event in the form of a summer school of 10 days, which was not interrupted by breaks and remote work, was more successful and accepted by participants. We also saw that the selection of cases needed to be done with care to allow participants to have the feeling of success in this short period of time. Team composition

needed to be handled with special care in order to have all the required skills at place. If this was not the case, skills would need to be provided by the organizational team or another case selected that fits the skills of the team better.

The analysis also highlighted the importance of a coach, who helped the teams to plan their activities and supports them in keeping all the reins together. This aspect was true for both the long- and short-term format.

Input sessions that provided training on specific skills were perceived as important, especially if they supported the concrete work with the careables; the same is true for the introduction to and application of the design thinking process; which was one of the most appreciated inputs for participants; the hands-on experience in co-designing the cases made participants experience that the direct contact with the case owners considerable influenced the way to approach and constructed the careables. It deepened the participants' empathy and the understanding of the case owners' needs.

The evaluation also showed how important the presence of the case owners was from a motivational point of view. When the workload increased and participants struggled with the complexity of projects it was crucial that the case owner was physically present and interacting with the team members. It increased the motivation of the participants and their commitment to help him/her became especially important.

Overall, the evaluation data highlights three aspects that need to be supported in order to motivate participants' engagement: 1. social embeddedness, 2. competence (having the feeling that one alone or the group have the competence to complete the task) and 3. autonomy in the co-creation work. All three aspects are key pillars of the self-determination theory (Ryan and Deci, 2000) and can be purposefully supported: 1) Social embeddedness can be stimulated through the team work, the presence of the case owner and the attentiveness of the organizational team; 2) competence can be strengthened through a thorough compilation of the team according to their individual competences, input sessions, and the expertise of the coaches; and 3) autonomy can be supported through a certain freedom in choosing what to try out, what instruments to use, what material to use.

The most important barrier, when all the things mentioned above are in place, is the aspect of time - a scarce resource of all participants. This is why the short term format that borrows ten days from students and interested makers and health professionals is a good format to come up with some careables and make a very intensive introduction to the topic of DIY health and care; the long-term format (3 months) dealt with the aspect of time by distributing engagement across several weeks of "light" engagement. For a more sustainable involvement we also need to think about additional ways of engaging people, as students for instance have limited time budget they can dedicate too much time to voluntary work, the same is true for makers etc.

On the tools side, the first analysis of user acceptance factors of the careables and welder platform shows that there is a huge interest in such a platform – all participants of the testing appreciated the idea behind it. This is the general feedback we get whenever we talk about the platform. What the user testing shows (and this is just a quick insight as more details will be presented in the next deliverable) we have to take specific care of the wording we use. It should not only address makers but also people in the need for help, their families and health care providers. Thus, terms like DIY, digital fabrication, maker etc. need to be explained as they are hardly known outside of the maker community. Different target groups need to be slowly introduced to the topic, like “taking them by the hand” and leading them through the content of the platform that might be interesting to them. Personal stories are a good way to show people what careable is all about, or the careables themselves that attract a lot of attention and a better understanding of what careable is all about.

The evaluation activities in the last year will specifically focus on different stakeholders' journeys through our platform and how to optimize them. This will specifically support objective 1 and 4 in Figure 23 above. We will start interviewing case owners to understand the long-term impact of the careables project and also what drives and hinders impacts to take place. We will continue the assessment of the co-creation activities and also enrich the analysis by looking into impacts that we might generate on a more political level.

8. References

Ryan, Richard M., and Edward L. Deci. "Self-determination theory and the facilitation of intrinsic motivation, social development, and well-being." *American psychologist* 55.1 (2000): 68.